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National Idea and Universal Ideological Processes

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Abstract: *The national idea and general ideological processes are of paramount importance for strengthening and developing national statehood. This article analyzes the concept of the national idea, its history, stages of development and its place in the modern world. General ideological processes, their role and impact in the context of globalization are also considered. The close interconnection of the national idea and general ideological processes, their mutual influence and significance in shaping national identity are highlighted.*

Key words: *National idea, general ideological processes, national statehood, globalization, national identity, education, culture, history, strengthening, development.*

The national idea is an ideology that forms based on a nation's historical, cultural, and spiritual heritage, reflecting its aspirations and national interests. The national idea serves as a unifying force for the people, strengthening their belief in the future. Universal ideological processes, on the other hand, are phenomena that occur worldwide, ensuring cooperation and integration among different nations. This article analyzes the interconnection between the national idea and universal ideological processes, as well as their impact on national statehood and spirituality.

The Concept of National Idea and Its History

The concept of the national idea has existed since ancient times, playing a crucial role in the historical development of every nation. For example, in Uzbekistan, great figures like Amir Temur and Alisher Navoi made significant contributions to shaping the national idea and national spirituality. The national idea plays a vital role in ensuring the unity and solidarity of the people and preserving their national identity.

Stages of Development of the National Idea

The development stages of the national idea are primarily related to historical conditions, socio-political circumstances, and the cultural progress of the people. Initially, the national idea was shaped during the people's struggle for freedom and independence. Later, after the declaration of state

independence, it found expression in state-building, economic development, and cultural advancement¹.

The National Idea in the Independence Period

During the independence period, the national idea became even more solidified, playing a crucial role in maintaining the unity and national identity of the people. In this period, the national idea was recognized as the foundation of state policy and served as an essential tool for achieving significant successes in economic and social spheres. The national idea also plays a significant role in educating the younger generation during the years of independence.

Universal Ideological Processes and Their Role in Globalization

Globalization processes have intensified economic, political, cultural, and scientific relations between countries worldwide today. These processes provide new opportunities for national states while also bringing various threats. Universal ideological processes play an essential role in enriching national ideas and spirituality and strengthening international cooperation.

Globalization and National Culture

Globalization processes contribute to the enrichment of national cultures and promote exchange among them. However, at the same time, globalization poses a risk of absorbing national cultures. The national idea serves as a crucial tool in preserving and enriching national culture in this process.

The History of Universal Ideological Processes

The history of universal ideological processes is primarily associated with international relations, diplomatic ties, and cultural exchanges. Universal ideological processes have developed through cultural, scientific, and economic relations between different nations. These processes have played an essential role in ensuring international cooperation and integration.

Universal Ideological Processes and Scientific-Technical Development

Scientific and technical development is also an important component of universal ideological processes. Achievements in science and technology strengthen the exchange of experiences between different nations, and these processes significantly influence the development of the national idea².

The Integral Connection Between National Idea and Universal Ideological Processes

The national idea and universal ideological processes are integrally connected, complementing each other. The national idea plays a crucial role in preserving the national identity and cultural heritage of the people. Universal ideological processes, in turn, help the national idea develop and harmonize with the modern world's demands. These processes contribute to the strengthening and development of national states.

National Spirituality and Education

The national idea and universal ideological processes also hold significant importance in national spirituality and educational processes. National spirituality encompasses the people's moral values,

¹ Karimov, I.A. (2016). "Uzbekistan: National Independence, Economy, Politics, Ideology." Tashkent: Uzbekistan.

² Mirziyoyev, Sh. (2021). "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan." Tashkent: Uzbekistan.

cultural heritage, and educational traditions. Universal ideological processes help this spirituality adapt to modern times, assimilating international experiences³.

National Idea and Culture

The national idea also plays an essential role in the cultural life of the people. Culture is an expression of the national idea, reflected in the people's art, literature, music, and other cultural manifestations. Universal ideological processes help enrich national culture and strengthen cultural ties between different nations.

National Idea and History

The national idea is related to the historical development of the people and is of great importance in preserving their historical heritage. Historical events, great figures, and the people's struggles for freedom play an essential role in shaping the national idea. Universal ideological processes help this historical heritage be recognized internationally and spread widely among the world's peoples.

National Idea and Economic Development

The national idea is also of great importance in the economic development process. It plays a significant role in protecting the people's economic interests, strengthening the national economy, and increasing its competitiveness. Universal ideological processes help the national economy integrate into the global economic system and develop international economic relations.

Conclusion

The national idea and universal ideological processes are of great importance in the development of national statehood and spirituality. Their interconnection and mutual influence play a significant role in protecting national interests, preserving and developing national identity.

The national idea is a crucial tool in preserving and developing the people's historical, cultural, and spiritual heritage, ensuring their unity and solidarity. This idea plays an important role in the implementation of strategies aimed at progress in economic, political, and cultural fields as the main part of state policy.

Universal ideological processes, in turn, have a significant impact on the development of the national idea in the context of globalization. Cooperation between different nations, scientific-technical progress, and cultural exchanges contribute to the enrichment of national culture. At the same time, globalization processes create new opportunities to preserve and develop national culture and traditions.

In-depth study and adaptation of national ideas and universal ideological processes to modern conditions is one of the urgent tasks of today. These processes contribute to the strengthening and development of national states, play a crucial role in preserving national identity, and protecting national interests⁴.

Moreover, the national idea and universal ideological processes play a significant role in educating the younger generation. They encourage young people to respect national values, historical heritage, and cultural traditions, to understand and develop their national identity. At the same time, universal

³ Safarov, B. (2019). "Globalization and National Idea." Tashkent: Ma'naviyat.

⁴ Bekmurodov, B. (2017). "National Idea in Uzbekistan's Independence Period." Tashkent: Adolat.

ideological processes help young people acquire modern knowledge and skills and broaden their worldview.

Therefore, adapting national ideas and universal ideological processes to modern demands, developing them on a scientific basis, and considering them from the perspective of national interests serve the strengthening of national statehood and the rise of national spirituality. These processes are of great importance in ensuring the national unity of the people, strengthening their economic and cultural progress, and creating a solid foundation for future generations.

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